

Nonisothermal Mold Filling in Resin Transfer Molding and Structural Reaction Injection Molding

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ABSTRACT

A numerical model for non-isothermal mold filling and curing simulation in thin cavities with preplaced fiber mats was developed based on the control volume method. Both lumped temperature system (i.e. local thermal equilibrium between the resin and the fiber) and un-lumped temperature system (i.e. thermal non-equilibrium locally) were considered. A Lagrangian coordinate system was used in the flow front region to improve the energy transfer calculation. Several molding simulation results were presented to show the effect of fiber mat presence (in the mold cavity) on the inlet pressure and temperature distribution.

KEYWORDS: Resin Transfer Molding; Mold Filling; Curing; Simulation; Molding Experiment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) and structural reaction molding (SRIM) are processes in which two liquid monomers or prepolymers are mixed and injected into a mold cavity where fiber mats are preplaced. The heat generated in RTM/SRIM processes is produced by the polymerization exotherm. The polymerization can usually be activated in two ways: mixing activated systems or thermally activated systems [1,2].

Because of the reaction exotherm and the energy conducted from the mold walls and convected by the flow, heat transfer cannot be neglected during the filling stage of RTM/SRIM processes. Moreover, resin viscosity changes as a function of temperature and conversion. Before the reaction starts, viscosity is temperature dependent and decreases with increasing temperature. However, when the crosslinking polymerization occurs, viscosity may become conversion sensitive and increase rapidly with increasing conversion. The interaction between fluid flow, heat transfer, reaction conversion, and resin viscosity complicates the governing equations. Some researchers considered two-dimensional isothermal mold filling in RTM by applying Darcy's law and either the finite element method [3,4], the finite difference method with numerical grid generation [5], or the boundary element method [6]. Young *et al.*[7,8] used the control volume approach to simulate the 3-D mold filling for complicated geometry in RTM based on Darcy's equation. Their model can also handle different fiber orientation, permeability changes, and multiple gates. For the non-isothermal mold filling in the RTM process, there was only one work appearing in the literature. Gonzalez[2] considered a simple one-dimensional thin cavity problem. He used non-local thermal equilibrium (i.e. two energy equations) to get two dimensionless temperature expressions in the integral form. He then used experimental temperature profiles to fit the heat transfer coefficient between the resin and the fiber mat based on the assumption that the heat transfer coefficient depended on the flow rate.

This study focused the effort on the analysis of non-isothermal mold filling in thin cavities with pre-placed fiber mats. To narrow the scope of the analysis, the channeling effect, fiber mat deformation during mold filling and heat transfer through the mold walls were neglected.

2. FORMULATION

The equations which describe flow through porous media for an incompressible fluid with chemical reaction take the general form

(i) mass balance:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{V} = 0, \quad (1)$$

(ii) momentum balance:

$$\vec{V} = - \frac{\bar{K}}{\mu} \cdot \nabla P \quad (2)$$

Here μ is the resin viscosity and the permeability tensor

$$\bar{K} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{XX} & K_{XY} & K_{XZ} \\ K_{YX} & K_{YY} & K_{YZ} \\ K_{ZX} & K_{ZY} & K_{ZZ} \end{bmatrix}$$

(iii) a. energy balance in the fluid:

$$\phi \rho_r c_{pr} \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial t} + \phi \rho_r c_{pr} (\vec{V} \cdot \nabla T_r) = \phi \nabla \cdot \mathbf{k}_r \nabla T_r + \phi h_v (T_r - T_r) + \phi \Phi + \phi \dot{G} \quad (3)$$

(iii) b. energy balance in the solid:

$$(1 - \phi) \rho_f c_{pr} \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} = (1 - \phi) \nabla \cdot \mathbf{k}_f \nabla T_f + \phi h_v (T_r - T_r) \quad (4)$$

(iv) species mass balance:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \vec{V} \cdot \nabla \alpha = \nabla \cdot D \nabla \alpha + m \quad (5)$$

where ϕ is porosity, ρ is density, c_p is specific heat, k is thermal conductivity, h_v is the volume heat transfer coefficient from the fluid to the fiber mat, and Φ is the viscous dissipation rate. G is the heat generation rate by chemical reaction or other sources and m is the mass generation rate of the polymer; α is the conversion of chemical species, and D is the mass diffusivity of polymer component into monomer component and *vice-versa*.. Subscript f stands for fiber mat, and r for resin fluid.

In the mold filling stage of RTM/SRIM, the viscous dissipation is usually insignificant compared with other contributions such as heat transfer between the resin fluid and the fiber mat or reaction exotherm. The mass diffusion is also negligible during the polymerization process because the chemical reaction rate is often much higher than the mass diffusion rate. For thin mold cavities, the flow may be simplified to a two-dimensional problem, but heat transfer is still in the three-dimensional form because heat convection in the planar direction and heat conduction in the gapwise direction are both significant. To handle mold cavities with complicated geometry, it is convenient to use a local coordinate system which describes the heat transfer and resin flow locally. This requires a coordinate transformation from the global system (X, Y, Z) to the local system (x, y, z) in such a way that the z axis is always normal to the cavity surface at every local position [8].

Eqns. (1) - (5) can be written in the local coordinate system for thin mold cavities.

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{u}(x,y) \\ \bar{v}(x,y) \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} s_{xx} & s_{xy} \\ s_{yx} & s_{yy} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial P(x,y)}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial P(x,y)}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

Where

$$\begin{bmatrix} s_{xx} & s_{xy} \\ s_{yx} & s_{yy} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{h_z} \int_{-\frac{h_z}{2}}^{\frac{h_z}{2}} \frac{1}{\mu(x,y,z)} \begin{bmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} \\ K_{yx} & K_{yy} \end{bmatrix} dz, \quad (8)$$

$$\phi \rho_r c_{pr} \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial t} + \phi \rho_{pr} c_r (\bar{u} \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial x} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial y}) = \phi k_r (\frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial z^2}) + \phi h_v (T_r - T_f) + \phi \dot{G}, \quad (9)$$

$$(1 - \phi) \rho_r c_{pr} \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial t} = (1 - \phi) k_r (\frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_r}{\partial z^2}) + \phi h_v (T_r - T_f), \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \bar{u} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} = m \quad (11)$$

Where s_{ij} 's are the flow coefficients with average values of viscosity and permeability in the gapwise direction, and h_z is the gapwise thickness. In Eqns. (6) - (11), the velocity is averaged out through the gapwise direction (for details, see Reference [8]). The initial conditions for Eqns. (9) - (11) are

$$T_r|_{\text{initial}} = T_{r0}, \quad T_r|_{\text{initial}} = T_{r0}, \quad \alpha|_{\text{initial}} = 0 \quad (12)$$

The boundary conditions for Eqns. (7) and (9)-(11) in the local coordinate system are

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial n} \Big|_{\text{wall}} = 0, \quad P|_{\text{front}} = 0, \quad P|_{\text{gate}} = P_0 \quad \text{or} \quad \bar{v}|_{\text{gate}} = \bar{v}_0$$

$$T_r|_{\text{wall}} = T_w, \quad T_r|_{\text{gate}} = T_{r0}, \quad \frac{\partial T_r}{\partial n} \Big|_{\text{front}} = 0, \quad T_r|_{\text{wall}} = T_w, \quad T_r|_{\text{gate}} = T_{r0}, \quad T_r|_{\text{front}} = T_{r0}, \quad \alpha|_{\text{gate}} = 0 \quad (13)$$

Where T_w is the cavity wall temperature, T_{r0} is the initial fluid temperature, and T_{f0} is the initial fiber mat temperature and equal to the cavity wall temperature T_w . Adiabatic boundary condition for resin fluid at the flow front and the mold-resin interface is assumed where n is the direction normal to the interface. In most of the molding processes, the resin flow is supplied either by a displacement controlled or a pressure controlled pumping device. Thus, the inlet condition can be either constant pressure or constant flow rate.

If the process can be assumed to be in local thermal equilibrium (i.e., the temperature is the same at a local position for both resin fluid and fiber mat), then Eqns. (9) and (10) can be combined into one equation. This is adequate when the heat transfer coefficient between the fiber mat and the resin fluid is large, the resin flow is very slow, or the solid grains are very fine. The one equation expression based on the weight average values between the fiber mat and the resin fluid is

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \phi \rho_r c_{pr} (\bar{u} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}) = k (\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2}) + \phi G \quad (14)$$

The initial and boundary conditions for the energy equation (14) become

$$T|_{\text{wall}} = T_w, \quad T|_{\text{gate}} = T_{r0}, \quad k \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} |_{\text{front}} = (1 - \phi) \rho_r c_{pr} \bar{v}_n (T_{r0} - T) \quad (15)$$

The major contribution to the heat generation is the polymerization. The polymerization can be either a mixing activated system or a thermally activated system [1,2]. For different types of polymerizations the reaction kinetics may vary and more complicated kinetic models may be required [9]. For illustration, a simple kinetic model is used in this study as,

$$\dot{G} = \Delta H (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^{m_1}) (1 - \alpha)^{m_2}, \quad m = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^{m_1}) (1 - \alpha)^{m_2}, \quad (16)$$

where ΔH is the heat of reaction, m_1 and m_2 are constants. The rate constants k_1 and k_2 are expressed in the Arrhenius form:

$$k_1 = A_1 e^{-E_1/RT_{\text{obs}}}, \quad k_2 = A_2 e^{-E_2/RT_{\text{obs}}}, \quad (17)$$

The resin viscosity is a function of temperature and resin conversion. Initially, the viscosity is temperature dependent and decreases with increasing temperature. After the reaction starts, the resin viscosity may become conversion sensitive and increase rapidly with increasing resin conversion. Since the molecular weight is low, the resin fluid can be treated as a Newtonian fluid. The viscosity change for a reactive thermosetting fluid can be expressed here by a widely used model [10]

$$\mu = A_\mu e^{E_\mu/RT} \left[\frac{\alpha_g}{\alpha_g - \alpha} \right]^{A_v + B_v \alpha}, \quad (18)$$

where α_g is the gel conversion, E_μ is the activation energy, and A_v and B_v are constants.

Again, this model is a typical rheological model and is used here for illustration. For different types of polymerizations, the viscosity models may vary [11,12].

3. SOLUTION METHOD

Before applying any numerical schemes to the above mentioned mass, flow, and energy equations, the heat conduction in the gapwise direction requires special consideration. To discretize this term, the finite difference method [13], collocation method, or other interpolation functions can be used. Here, the Chebyshev collocation spectral method is used [14-16] to solve the energy and conversion balances in the gapwise direction, because it gave an exponential convergence rate for a smooth function and a more accurate solution than other methods [16].

The heat conduction term in the gapwise direction is discretized as follows: choosing the zeros of the N^{th} order Chebyshev function as the collocation points and changing variables to the dimensionless form such that z is defined on $[-1, 1]$, i.e.

$$k \frac{\partial^2 T_j}{\partial z^2} = \frac{4k}{h_z^2} \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} d_{j,l}^{(2)} T_l, \quad (19)$$

where $d_{i,j}^{(2)}$ is the component of the coefficient tensor of the second order derivative. Eqns. (14) and (11) are re-written as:

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T_j}{\partial t} + \phi \rho_r c_{pr} (\bar{u} \frac{\partial T_j}{\partial x} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial T_j}{\partial y}) = k \frac{\partial^2 T_j}{\partial x^2} + k \frac{\partial^2 T_j}{\partial y^2} + \frac{4k}{h_z^2} \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} d_{j,l}^{(2)} T_l + \phi \Delta H (k_1 + k_2 \alpha_j^{m_1}) (1 - \alpha_j)^{m_2} \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_j}{\partial t} + \bar{u} \frac{\partial \alpha_j}{\partial x} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \alpha_j}{\partial y} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha_j^{m_1}) (1 - \alpha_j)^{m_2} \quad (21)$$

where $j=0,1,2,\dots,N-1$.

The T_j 's and α_j 's are the temperature and conversion at the collocation points. Equations (9) and (10) can be handled the same way. It is noted that Eqns. (20) and (21) consist of two N sets of coupled two-dimensional equations. In the next stage, the control volume method is applied to the flow equation (7), energy equation (20), and the species balance equation (21) [8].

4. NUMERICAL SCHEME

To start the numerical formulation, the surface of the mold cavity is discretized into a family of three-node triangular elements. Because of the nature of the mesh generated in this method, the grids are fixed. Consequently, the physical flow front may be markedly different from the "numerical" flow front as shown in Figure 1a and 1b. Thus, performing an accurate energy balance calculation near the flow front region is difficult and requires some numerical rearrangement. In order to distinguish the flow front region from the main flow region, we need to consider the filled volume fraction, f . The filled volume fraction, f , is zero for empty control volumes and unity for fully filled control volumes. The control volumes with $0 < f < 1$ are considered as the flow front region, while the control volumes with $f=1$ are considered as the main flow region. A simple way to solve the governing equations is to neglect the flow front region and handle it as an interface condition, as explained in Figure 1a. This is convenient because the computation domains, where only the main flow region is considered, are the same for both the flow equation and the energy equation(s). This is adequate for the flow equation since the pressure at the flow front region vanishes and does not play an important role. However, this method cannot precisely account for the energy balance in the flow front region where heat exchange between the resin fluid and the fiber mat is the dominant factor in the heat transfer calculation. An improved way to handle the heat transfer in the flow front region is described as follows.

It is assumed that if the difference of the filled volume fraction of a control volume, f , between the previous time step and the current time step is greater than zero, the control volume is in the flow front region. (see Fig. 1b) The energy equation or species mass balance equation in the flow front region is represented by a balance of energy or mass in a Lagrangian form as:

Lumped Temperature System

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D}{Dt} \int_{cs} f \cdot \rho c_p T_j ds = f \cdot k \int_{\Gamma} \frac{\partial T_j}{\partial n} d\Gamma + f \cdot \int_{cs} \frac{4k}{h_z^2} \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} d_{j,l}^{(2)} T_l ds + \frac{df}{dt} \cdot \int_{cs} (1 - \phi) \rho_r c_{pr} (T_{r0} - T_j) ds \\ + f \cdot \int_{cs} \phi \Delta H (k_1 + k_2 \alpha_j^{m_1}) (1 - \alpha_j)^{m_2} ds \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Un-Lumped Temperature System

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D}{Dt} \int_{cs} \phi \rho_r c_{pr} T_{rj} ds = \int_{\Gamma} \phi k_r \frac{\partial T_{rj}}{\partial n} d\Gamma + \int_{cs} \phi \frac{4k_r}{h_z^2} \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} d_{j,l}^{(2)} T_{rl} ds + \int_{cs} \phi h_v (T_{\eta} - T_{rj}) ds \\ + \int_{cs} \phi \Delta H (k_1 + k_2 \alpha_j^{m_1}) (1 - \alpha_j)^{m_2} ds \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D}{Dt} \int_{cs} (1-\phi) \rho_r c_{pr} T_0 ds = \int_{\Gamma} (1-\phi) k_r \frac{\partial T_{\eta}}{\partial n} d\Gamma + \int_{cs} (1-\phi) \frac{4k_r}{h_z^2} \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} d_{j,l}^{(2)} T_{\eta} ds + \\ \int_{cs} \phi h_v (T_{rj} - T_{\eta}) ds \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The species mass balance equation in the flow front region for both systems becomes

$$\frac{D}{Dt} \int_{cs} \alpha_j ds = \int_{cs} [k_1 + k_2 \alpha_j^{m_1}] [1 - \alpha_j]^{m_2} ds \quad (25)$$

In Eqn. (22), the internal energy change of a system is balanced by the heat conducted through the system's boundary, the heat absorbed from the fiber bed which depends on the changing rate of the filled volume fraction, df/dt , and the chemical reaction exotherm.

There are many ways to solve initial value problems. The explicit finite difference method takes advantage of a simple formulation; however, it is conditionally stable. A stability analysis of the explicit upwind finite difference method for a one-dimensional wave equation [17] has shown that stability depends on the Courant number. The Courant number is defined as (velocity x time interval) / (grid size). A Courant number less than 1 ensures stability. In the control volume method, it is very difficult to define a criterion under which the explicit finite difference method is stable because the meshes do not have the same size. Thus, the implicit finite difference method is chosen here. In addition to the stability problem, another important consideration in the numerical scheme is solution accuracy. Large truncation errors may result in a meaningless solution even though the scheme is stable. The numerical aliasing and diffusion errors (both of them are called the truncation errors) are sensitive to the flow velocity, mesh size, and time step if the flow is advection dominant. Since the Courant number is an important factor in determining the time step size, an equivalent Courant number should be defined.

The largest Courant number in all the triangular elements is chosen as the equivalent Courant number. Mathematically the equivalent Courant number is:

$$C_{ert} = \text{Max} \left(\frac{|\bar{v}| \Delta t}{\Delta x} \right)_{e=1}^m, \quad (26)$$

where Δx is the smallest side of each triangular element, $|\bar{v}|$ is the magnitude of velocity for each element, and Δt is the time increment. The time step is constrained such that only one control volume is allowed to be completely filled [7,8] in an increment.

The Δt is then divided into n numbers of sub-time steps by satisfying

$$\text{Int} \left(\frac{C_{ert}}{fct} \right) = n, \quad (27)$$

where fct is a given value which should be between 0.7 ~ 1.1 for the best accuracy [17], and $\text{Int}()$ means integer of (). By this checking procedure, we can ensure our solution to be as accurate as possible, although the truncation error is still very difficult to control because the mesh sizes vary from element to element.

5. NUMERICAL SIMULATION

Some simulation results of the lumped temperature system and the un-lumped temperature system are presented here. One mold was an automobile hood which had a complicated geometry and a thickness of 0.003m everywhere. The gate was chosen at the center of the cavity. The cavity was preplaced with the preheated random fiber mats with a porosity of 0.7 everywhere. The resin injection rate for the hood cavity was kept constant at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

The temperature of the cavity walls were kept at 75°C , while the initial resin temperature was

20°C. The chosen kinetic and rheological parameters, and material properties of the resin and fiber were listed in Tables 1 - 3.

Numerical simulation of both the filling and the curing stages was also carried out in a circular thin cavity. The cavity was 0.3 m diameter and 0.013 m thick. The flow rate was 2.77×10^{-5} m³/s, and the porosity of the random fiber mat was 0.8. The wall and initial fiber mat temperatures were taken as 75°C and the initial resin temperature was 20°C. The kinetic and rheological parameters, and material properties of the resin and the fiber were the same as in the previous cases except that $\Delta H = 140$ Joule/g.

Figures 2 and 3 show simulation results of temperature and conversion for an automobile hood mold. Such information would be useful for both part design and processing condition selection.

Figure 4 presents the simulation results of both mold filling and curing in a circular cavity. In this figure, 1c is located 4.51 cm from the inlet, and 2c is located 8.5 cm from the inlet. Both 1c and 2c are in the middle plane, while 1s is located 0.5 cm right above 1c. T_{1c} and T_{2c} have similar temperature profiles except T_{2c} has a higher temperature at any instant of time before it reaches the maximum temperature due to more heat absorption from the fiber. The temperatures T_{1c} and T_{2c} decrease in the filling stage, and increase to a maximum during the curing stage. Because, at the middle plane, the heat transfer during the filling stage is mainly caused by the convection, the temperature at each location begins to decrease after the cold resin touches the hot fiber until the filling ends. During the curing stage, the temperatures increase as a result of polymerization exotherm. After reaching the maximum, the temperatures decrease because the large temperature difference between the mold walls and the composite in the gapwise direction, which results in heat being transferred to the walls. Since the resin at 2c has almost been cured after T_{2c} reaches the maximum, the reaction exotherm there becomes smaller thereafter; in the mean time, the reaction at 1c is still going on. Consequently, Figure 4 shows that T_{2c} becomes lower than T_{1c} at the later stage of curing.

The temperature T_{1s} has a different trend compared to the T_{1c} curve. This is because heat transfer there is affected by both heat convection in the planar direction and heat conduction in the gapwise direction. Temperature decreases first then increases quickly during the filling stage due to the heat conducted from the walls. However, the temperature during the curing stage does not increase as much as T_{1c} and T_{2c} . Because the polymerization exotherm can be released into the mold wall faster than that at location 1c after the resin temperature becomes higher than the wall temperature. The conversion distribution indicates that the conversion near the wall is higher than that near the center at the filling stage and the early part of the curing stage. At the latter part of the curing stage, the conversion near the wall becomes lower because of the lower temperature.

A comparison of lumped temperature system and un-lumped temperature system during filling is shown in Figure 5. The mold geometry and initial and boundary conditions are the same as in the previous case except the flow rate and the volumetric heat transfer coefficient. The flow rate in this case (6.75×10^{-4} m³/s, simulating the SRIM process) is 25 times that in the previous case (simulating the RTM process), and the h_v is assumed to be 0.25. The temperature profiles of the lumped temperature system at different locations are presented in Figure 5 (a). All the temperatures T_{1c} , T_{2c} and T_{3c} decrease during filling. When the resin encounters the fiber mat, there is a sharp decrease in temperature because of the local thermal equilibrium assumption. The simulated temperature difference between locations 1c and 3c at the end of filling is about 18 °C.

The temperature profiles of the un-lumped temperature system are shown in Figure 5 (b). The fiber temperatures at different locations decrease gradually during filling, while the resin temperatures at these locations increase initially due to the heat conduction from the hotter fiber mat but decrease toward the end of filling because of the heat convection effect of the colder incoming resin. The simulated temperature difference of resin between locations 1c and 3c at the end of filling is less than 8 °C.

Since curing rate depends strongly on the resin temperature, an accurate prediction of temperature distribution in the mold cavity is necessary. At high flow rates, the un-lumped temperature system should be used for the simulation.

6. REFERENCES

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ΔH (J/g)	A_1 (1/min)	A_2 (1/min)	
225	2.27E7	4.07E7	
E_1 (kcal/mol)	E_2 (kcal/mol)	m_1	m_2
13	12	0.3	1.7

Table 1 Kinetic parameters of resin used in simulation

A_{η} (Pa-s)	E_{η} (kJ/mol)	A_v	B_v
2.78E-4	18	1.5	1

Table 2 Rheological parameters of resin used in simulation

Properties	ρ (g/m ³)	c_p (J/g \cdot k)	k (j/m-s ² -k)
resin	1.1E6	1.68	0.168
fiberglass	2.56E6	0.67	0.0335

Table 3 Material properties of resin and fiber used in simulation

Figure 1a A simple method for heat transfer calculation during flow.

Figure 1b An improved method for heat transfer calculation during flow in the main flow region and the flow front region.

Figure 2 Isotherms at the end of mold filling in an automotive hood cavity with preplaced random fiber mats (lumped temperature system).

- 1--7.33E-3
 2--1.47E-2
 3--2.20E-2

Figure 3 Conversion contours at the end of mold filling in an automotive hood cavity with preplaced random fiber mats (lumped temperature system).

Figure 4 Temperature and conversion profiles at different locations during the filling and curing stages in a circular cavity with preplaced random fiber mats; subscript 1 is 4.51 cm from inlet and subscript 2 is 8.5 cm from inlet (lumped temperature system).

Figure 5 Temperature profiles of the resin and the fiber during the filling stage in a circular cavity with preplaced random fiber mats: (a) lumped temperature system, (b) un-lumped temperature system (1c is 4.51 cm from inlet, 2c is 8.5 cm from inlet, and 3c is 12.5 cm from inlet).

